

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENT CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS BASED ON THE COMPETENCE APPROACH

F.K.Payanova

Assistant of Termez Institute of Engineering and Technology

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Abstract. *In higher education, psychological factors of the development of independent creative activity of students are analyzed in connection with the intellectual, emotional and motivational sphere, and the role of motivation, purposefulness, emotions, personal qualities, reflection plays a huge role in the methodological improvement of physics teaching. This article discusses the psychological aspects of the development of independent creative activity of students based on the competence approach.*

Keywords: *competence, activity, temperament, psychological, reflex, aesthetic, character, individual, creative, test, motive.*

Topic statement. In higher education, the psychological factor of the development of independent creative activity of students is analyzed in connection with the intellectual, emotional and motivational sphere, and in the methodical improvement of the teaching of physics, motivation, purpose, emotion, personality, and reflection are of great importance. It is known that one of the components of education is the education realized in the first and second stages of the process of social development of a person. Personality development can be considered as a process of gaining social experience. This is a two-step process. In the first stage, the basic social and psychological values of a person are formed; labor, moral, aesthetic, political, legal, environmental and family, etc. The second stage; related to the acquisition of one or another profession and specialty by a person. This is the process of professional socialization of a person.

A person develops not only under the influence of a genetic factor or the surrounding social environment, but not under the mechanical effects of these or those aspects, but in the process of internal conflicts, which provides solutions that go from simple to complex. The formation of the human personality in connection with the process of his psychic development, expressed more by education, occupies a central place throughout his activity. According to the famous Russian psychologist L.S.Vygotsky, "The main goal of the teacher's activity is to organize the cooperation of students with each other, of teachers with students, to direct and regulate the activities of students through collective activities."

Education is a type of activity that helps a person acquire a number of characteristics. For example, if a student sets himself the goal of understanding the material and strives for it, he will develop determination and perseverance, and a student who begins to study the entire course independently will develop a certain scheme of actions and will develop characteristic features such as independence and entrepreneurship.

The famous Polish psychologist, Professor Ya.Strelyau, wrote about temperament as follows: we are interested in the temperament of an individual and express his behavior in the form of an answer to the question "How", how does he behave in a certain situation? What will be the actions, what will be the reaction? etc.

Temperament depends on the type and characteristics of the nervous system, it is a gift of nature. Temperament determines the dynamics of mental activity, and students with different temperaments differ in the speed of receiving information, development of methods of mental and practical activity. Therefore, for them, different methods and different pace of educational work, in particular, different number of strengthening exercises are required.

Temperament is general activity (quick completion of all tasks, arguments), dominance (constant desire to lead, protection of one's rights), courage (not expressing fear, sense of danger), self-confidence, calmness, approachability (constant desire to talk with people), reflexivity (self-analysis, analysis of past events), depression (emotional and mental depression), emotionality (ease of evoking feelings), self-control, objectivity (ability to objectively assess), goodwill, tolerance (being polite, not being disturbed by negative influences) [26, 25 b].

The characteristics of human temperament are so wide that it is impossible to show all of them.

The teacher must be able to determine the temperament of the student, that is, whether the student is sanguine or melancholic, he must adapt to each type of temperament around him. It is very difficult to change individual characteristics and qualities (a gift of nature), but knowing them can prevent tension at school and in interpersonal relationships. In general, the teacher's task is not to determine the student's temperament, but to observe which characteristics are actively manifested in him, which words and actions are effective. is to observe that it affects [26, 20 b].

Currently, pedagogy requires students to create a method that meets the requirements of the time. Both the object and the subject of the learning process are the student. Each student is characterized by his individual psychological characteristics. in psychology to treat students according to their character:

- when working with choleric, it is impossible to speak rudely, get angry, because they have a negative response reaction;
- Sanguines should be constantly challenged to concentrate their thoughts, asking new, more complex and interesting questions;
- Phlegmatics should be actively involved in the educational process, students of this type want to pay special attention to themselves;
- melancholics want to pay special attention to themselves, to hear praise for their success. Do not fight them, do not raise your voice [56].

Education is a type of activity that helps a person acquire a number of characteristics. For example, if a student sets himself the goal of understanding the material and strives for it, he will develop determination and perseverance, and a student who begins to study the entire course independently will develop a certain scheme of actions and will develop characteristic features such as independence and entrepreneurship.

As Ushinsky said, if pedagogy wants to educate a person in all aspects, first of all it is necessary to know him in all aspects.

According to experts, philosophers - games, psychologists - tests, didacts - the organization of a place of knowledge focused on personality. In addition, there are also methods of observation, questionnaires, interviews. They are traditional methods that have been used for a long time. It is emphasized that every pedagogue should stimulate the student's desire to learn during his activity.

It is useful for the physics teacher to conduct his own psychological test. The physical questions in the tests should correspond to the psychological aspects of the participants [26].

A child who decides to study well develops business acumen, the ability to listen to others, the ability to accept their point of view, the ability to defend his right opinion, the ability to work in cooperation with a group (because group work forms are often used in schools). If the educational form of working in groups (working in pairs, in groups) is often used in the course of the lesson, communicative competences are formed in students. If students are required to actively participate in classes (intensely), business skills are formed, such as concentration, movement according to the plan, and the correct application of knowledge.

A pressing problem in higher education is the problem of how to educate students in the context of increasingly rapid development. Of course, with the development of science, it is impossible not to take into account the fact that the ideas that students should master are more and more clearly defined.

Pedagogical factors were considered, such as academic knowledge, teaching paradigm, social culture of the people, methodical approach. In pedagogy:

1. Model of behavior. based on the competence approach, the student's independent creative activity is manifested in the student's creativity, interest in innovation, internal mental state, moral and ethical system of behavior, behavior and behavior. Therefore, the model of behavior is an important factor that encourages students' methodical ingenuity in Japanese education.

2. In the development of independent creative activity based on the competence approach, students engage in honest communication in order to form a sense of identity in the field of professional activity. Harmful environment, activities can be emaciated. Therefore, ensuring the possibility of improving the methodological skills of future engineers also depends on the performance factor.

Methodical practice is brought to the mind of the student in speech communication. Speech communication takes place in the classroom and improves students' methodological skills.

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